

ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF VARIOUS METHODS OF VISUALIZATION OF TOPOGRAPHIC FEATURES OF THE RELIEF OF MOUNTAIN LANDSCAPES

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Abstract: The article highlights the methods of visualization of topographic features of the relief of mountain landscapes and a comparative analysis is carried out. The mountain relief has a variety of shapes, it is three-dimensional in space that must be transmitted on a plane, which of course complicates the process. Therefore, maps for different purposes use different ways of depicting terrain, since each method has different advantages and disadvantages. Various ways of visualizing the relief from the XV century to the present day are analyzed. A digital terrain model of the Mirankul mountain peaks of the Samarkand region has been created using the GIS program "Panorama".

Keywords: relief, digital terrain model, mountain landscapes, perspective method, strokes, washing, elevations, horizontals, hypsometric method.

Introduction. In recent years, thematic mapping, including terrain mapping, has been developing due to the active use of geoinformation technologies, in particular geoinformation processing of digital terrain models (DTM). Representing a way of structurally describing such a fundamental part of geographical space as relief, DTM are of paramount importance in solving a wide range of geographical and cartographic tasks: modeling areas of flooding, planning the construction of infrastructure facilities, calculating the intake of solar radiation and many others [1].

Relief plays a key role among all the elements of a mountainous area, since it affects the distribution of hydrography, roads, vegetation, settlements and other components. These elements and the relief are interdependent with each other. Its image on the map presents certain difficulties, since it is required to convey volume in space, while the map displays the terrain in a plane. The relief has a variety of shapes, it is three-dimensional in space that must be transmitted on a plane, which of course complicates the process. Therefore, on maps of different purposes, different ways of depicting the terrain are used, let's consider them.

Methods. 1. The pictorial or perspective method is an arbitrary image of a mountainous area, which is based on how the relief is perceived by the eye. This method is based on imagination, since the cartographer does not rise above the Ground. Mountains are usually highlighted with shadows to enhance visibility.

Such an image does not ensure the correct transmission of the shapes of the earth's surface and distorts the position of objects applied in the planned outlines [2].

In the XV–XVIII centuries, the pictorial (perspective) method of depicting relief was widely used, which is currently mainly used on children's maps in order to ensure visibility, rather than accuracy.

Fig. 1 – Perspective signs for some morphological landscapes (according to E. Rais): 1 - glaciers (glaciers); 2 - highlands; 3 - alpine highlands; 4 - middle mountains; 5 - hilly areas; 6 - rejuvenated mountains; 7 - residual plain (peneplain); 8 - residual plain that has undergone rejuvenation; 9 - loess areas; 10 - moraine landscape; 11 - drumlins; 12 - fjords; 13 - alluvial sub-mountain fan plain; 14 - cuesta; 15 - plateau rejuvenated in arid conditions; 16 – volcanoes [2].

2. The method of strokes. In the XVIII century, the cartographic representation of the relief in a pictorial way was no longer sufficient, since they needed fast and accurate information about the steepness of the slopes, the presence of hydrography and settlements, the nature of the terrain and relief in general.

Results and discussion. The above-mentioned methods of visualization of topographic features of the relief of mountain landscapes have their advantages and disadvantages.

The positive property of the pictorial method is its clarity and simplicity, however, it does not provide geometric accuracy of relief transmission, therefore this method is more often used on children's maps.

The disadvantage of the stroke method is the inability to determine absolute and relative heights. In addition, creating strokes is a very time-consuming process, and printing maps requires high accuracy. Therefore, new methods of relief imaging have been developed. Currently, the dashed method is used to depict rocky terrain on topographic maps.

The method of washing the relief, or black-and-white plastic, gives us a visual plastic image of the mountain relief, but it is impossible to determine the steepness of the slopes and heights of the points on these maps. Currently, the method of relief washing is used on some small-scale general geographic maps (on political, political-administrative and administrative maps).

The elevation method makes it easier to read maps and gives accurate data on the exceedances of some points above others, but it is not used as an independent method, because this method does not give a clear and visual representation of the relief, it is more convenient to use it in combination with other methods of depicting the relief.

The horizontal method makes it possible to conveniently obtain information about the terrain, carry out various cartometric work, such as determining exceedances, steepness, slope direction, etc., therefore, this method is used on state topographic maps.

The hypsometric method or layered coloring of the height steps makes it possible to accurately measure the relief and perform various cartographic work on the map, the relief is easy to read, even mountainous, even flat. And if you also choose the colors of the scale successfully, then you can create the impression of a three-dimensional map.

The digital terrain model is currently the basis of digital mapping. DTM makes it possible to perform various calculations, construction of relief, sections, serves to model construction sites, mudflow zones, trails, profiles, to create land use plots, for example, construction sites and other design work. DTM can currently be built in various GIS programs, including IndorGIS, Autodesk Civil 3D, Panorama, etc.

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